

Influence of Drug Abuse on Academic Performance of Mathematics Students in Tertiary Institution

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Abstract

This Study investigate the Influence of Drug abuse on the academic performance of Students in tertiary institution with special reference to mathematics students in FCE Okene, Kogi state. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Four research questions and a hypothesis were raised to guide the study. The population of this study comprise of all mathematics students in federal college of education Okene, Kogi State, with the total population of 53 students whose major course is mathematics. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 40 mathematics students used for the study. A structured questionnaire on a 4-point rating scale was used for data collection. Frequency count and mean was used to analyze the data collected. Chi-Square (X^2) test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that mathematics students are aware of the causes of drug abuse but not fully aware about the dangers and side effects of drug abuse on the academic performance, there is correlation between mathematics students backgrounds with their drug use and academic performance, there is no significant relationship between the effects of drug abuse and academic performance among mathematics students in FCE Okene, Kogi State. The study recommended that there should be more awareness programs about the dangers of drug abused specifically targeting mathematics students, students should be offered workshops on stress management and coping skills which would reduce likelihood of Drug Abuse among mathematics students.

Keywords: Drug abuse, Mathematics, students, academic, performance.

Introduction

Drug abuse, also known as substance abuse, has become a pervasive issue globally, affecting individuals from various walks of life, including students in tertiary institutions (UNODC, 2020). The World

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Health Organization (2018) defines drug abuse as the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. Research has shown that drug abuse is prevalent among students in tertiary institutions, with studies indicating that 30-50% of students engage in substance abuse (Modebelu, O.Z. & Adeniyi, E. Oladipo. (2020).). This trend is alarming, as drug abuse can have severe consequences on students' academic performance, mental health, and overall well-being. The misuse of substances such as cannabis, alcohol, tramadol, and stimulants are increasingly affecting students' academic performance and overall wellbeing. Mathematics students, in particular, experience high cognitive demands, stress, and pressure to perform, which may increase their vulnerability to substance use. In the context of mathematics students, drug abuse can have particularly detrimental effects. Mathematics requires critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills, which can be impaired by substance abuse (Khan, A., Khan, S, Ababs, S.A & Khan M, 2019).

In Nigeria, where this study is focused, drug abuse among tertiary institution students is a growing concern. A study by the National Bureau of Statistics (2018) reported that 27% of students in tertiary institutions used illicit drugs. Amadi and Akpelu, (2018) conducted a research on drug abuse and academic performance of secondary school students in Emohua Local Government Area of River State. The findings of the study revealed that students commonly used drugs such as alcohol and hot drinks, tobacco, Indian hemp and marijuana. Peer group influence contributed to abuse of drugs by students and students who abused drugs recorded poor academic performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that students should be educated and enlightened about the dangers of drug abuse.

The above study focused on Drug abuse and academic performance of secondary school students while this current study focused on Drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students in tertiary institution. King (2016) carried out a study on influence of Drug Abuse on the academic performance of students in Tertiary Institution. A case study of FCE Abeokuta Ogun State. The findings of the study revealed that financial incapability of students, peer group and lifestyle of parent influence students to be addicted to drug abuse. It was also recommended that educational programme, should be organized for students to enlighten them on the dangers and implication in drug abuse.

Amadi and Akpelu, (2018) conducted a research on Drug abuse and academic performance of secondary school students in mathematics in Gokana Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study concluded that there is influence of drug abuse on academic performance on students; there is significant influence of drug abuse on academic performance on secondary school students based on gender, family types and family size. This study focused on the influence of drug abuse on academic performance of Mathematics students in tertiary institution a case study of Mathematics students with focus on Mathematics students in Federal College of Education, Okene, Kogi State.

Drug abuse among tertiary institution students has become a rising concern among many researchers. Despite efforts by various school authorities, health agencies and government to restraint this trend, there are still a growing number of students continue to engage in substance abuse daily, ranging from alcohol, marijuana, medications like tramadol, codeine and lots more. This problem is particularly

worrisome among mathematics students, whose academic success depends heavily on cognitive abilities such as critical thinking, memory, concentration, and logical reasoning. Drug abuse is known to impair mental function, memory retention, and logical reasoning, which are the core components necessary for excelling in mathematics.

Mathematics, a subject perceived as abstract and mentally demanding require students' full mental alertness and discipline. The impairment of mental functions caused by drug abuse directly conflicts with these academic demands. Students under the influence of drugs often struggle with punctuality, participation, attention span, and performance in assignments, tests, and examinations. Furthermore, there is a gap in existing literature specifically addressing the impact of drug abuse on mathematics students as a subgroup within tertiary education. While studies exist on drug abuse and academic performance, few studies explore the unique cognitive and psychological demands of mathematics, making it difficult to implement discipline-specific interventions.

If this issue is left unchecked, the long-term implications could include a decline in the quality of graduates in mathematical sciences, poor representation in global STEM fields, and loss of future innovators. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the extent to which drug abuse influences the academic performance of mathematics students and to identify strategies to mitigate this influence.

Research Questions

This study intends to answer the following questions:

1. What are the causes of drug abuse among mathematics students?
2. What are the effects of drug abuse on the academic performance of mathematics students?

Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students.

Research Method

A descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population of this study comprise of all 53 mathematics students in Federal College of Education, Okene, Kogi State across the three (3) academic programmed in the college. Simple random technique was used to select 40 respondents from both NCE Students and Undergraduate students.

The research instrument used in this study was a structured questionnaire on a 4-point Likert scale titled Drug Use and Academic Performance Questionnaire (DUAPQ), the respondents were given the opportunity to express their mind and opinions on the study by ticking the alternative which represents their views. The

research instrument was administered by the researcher and collected upon completion. In the process, no questionnaire was lost.

Data Analysis: descriptive statistics (frequency, mean) was used to analysed the research questions while inferential statistics (Chi-square) was used to test the research hypothesis at 95% significance level. A criterion of mean of 2.50 was set for decision making. A mean score of ≥ 2.50 was accepted otherwise, rejected.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What are the causes of drug among mathematics students?

Table 1. Responses on the causes of drug abuse among mathematics students

S/N	Items (Statement)	N	X	Remark
1.	The pressure to maintain high grades contributes to drug abuse among mathematics students	40	3.12	Accept
2.	The availability of drugs on campus influences the livelihood of drug abuse among mathematics students	40	2.90	Accept
3.	Peer group influence can leads to drug abuse among mathematics students	40	3.20	Accept
4.	Lack of proper education about the dangers of drug abuse can also lead to drug abuse among mathematics students.	40	3.30	Accept
5.	I believe that some mathematics students use drugs as a way to cope with academic stress	40	3.22	Accept

Table 1 above shows that the mean scores of all the items are above the bench mark mean of 2.5. this implies that they are accepted as the causes of drug abuse among mathematics students. Therefore, the pressure to maintain high grades, Peer group influence and lack of proper awareness about the dangers of drug abuse. These are perceived causes of drug abuse among mathematics students in Federal College of Education, Okene.

Research Question Two: What are the effects of drug abuse on the academic performance of mathematics students?

Table 2. Response of the effects of Drug Abuse among Mathematics Students.

S/N	Items (statement)	N	X	Remark
1.	Abuse of drugs increases attention, alertness and enhances effective learning of mathematics in classroom	40	2.11	Reject
2.	Drug abuse can interfere with academic performance and can create obstacles to learning mathematics	40	3.22	Accept

3. Students On Drug Perform Excellently in mathematics compare to other students.	40	1.98	Reject
4. Most drugs that are commonly abuse improve the brain and boost the nerves of function and therefore influence manipulation skills	40	2.05	Reject
5. My academic performance in mathematics have decrease ever since I state taking drugs	40	3.08	Accept

From Table 2 above, item 1, 3 and 4 are below the bench mark mean of 2.50. this implies that the abuse of drugs reduces attention, alertness and effective learning. Also, students abuse of drugs leads to a woeful performance in mathematics. While item 2 and 5 are above the mean mark of 2.50 which implies that drug abuse creates obstacles and interfere with students academic performance in mathematics. Also, academic performance will decrease as a result of drugs intakes. This shows the positive and negative effects of drug abuse among mathematics students in Federal College of Education Okene.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students.

Table 5. Chi-square computation:

	Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	0.255 ^a	1	0.614	
Continuity Correction ^b	0.087	1	0.768	
Likelihood Ratio	0.256	1	0.613	
Fisher's Exact Test				0.677
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.252	1	0.616	0.386
N of Valid Cases	100			

A Chi-Square test of independence was performed to evaluate the relationship between students' drug abuse and their academic performance. The result of the Pearson Chi-Square test of independence yielded a value of 0.255 and an asymptotic significance (2-sided) of 0.614. since the p -value (0.614) is

greater than the significance level of 0.05, we fail to reject the H_0 which state that there is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students. This implies that drug abuse does not have a statistically significant effect on mathematics students' academic performance in Federal College of Education, Okene based on the data obtained.

Discussion the Results

The first research question investigated the causes of drug abuse among mathematics students. The findings shows that mathematics students are aware of the causes of drugs abuse (positive result). This is because some of the causes of drug abuse among mathematics students investigated in this research work are common to the students. The findings revealed that the pressure to maintain high grades contributed to drug abuse among mathematics students. The findings is in line with the assertion of Edward (2014) who stated that peer group influence is one of the strongest motives which triggers students into drug abuse.

The second research question investigated the side effects of drug abuse on the academic performance of mathematics students. The study revealed that half of the students investigated are aware of the side effects of drug abuse while half of the students are not aware about the dangers and side effects of drug abuse. The findings of research question 2 also revealed that drug abuse has effect on the academic of mathematics students in FCE Okene. Drug abused alters the brain chemistry and interferes with the student's ability to make decision and concentrate in their academic work. It results in impairment of mental activities or capacity of the students and destabilize their body function and emotion for academic proficiency. This is in line with Adamu, and Tafida, (2024) that examined the impact of drug abuse on Academic performance of students in senior secondary schools in Bauchi State. Which is also supported by Abikwi and Okafor, (2022) that examined the effect of drug abuse on the academic performance of undergraduate students in Edo State.

Furthermore, the study test for significant relationship between drug abuse and mathematics students academic performance using Chi-square test of independence. The result of the test of hypothesis shows that there is no relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of mathematics students in FCE Okene, Kogi State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that mathematics students in FCE Okene are aware of the causes and effect of drug abuse. Drug abuse among mathematics students in tertiary institutions has a detrimental impact on academic performance. The study highlights the urgent need for intervention programs and ways to curb the menace cause by drug abuse among mathematics students in tertiary institutions. Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended among others that there should be more

awareness programs about the dangers of drug abuse specifically targeting mathematics students. Workshops on stress management and coping skills to reduce the likelihood of drug abuse among mathematics students should be encourage. Furthermore, counseling services should actively engage students struggling with substance abuse in the college. In like vein, there should be increase in students' extracurricular activities which can provide alternative to drug use and promote healthier social interaction. Strict enforcement of policies against drug abuse is necessary within educational institutions

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